

Geoweaver for Workflow Tangibility and Productivity at NASA

New Challenges Need New Software

<https://zenodo.org/records/11118247>

Ziheng Sun
George Mason University

<https://github.com/ESIP/pygeoweaver> | <https://github.com/ESIP/Geoweaver>

NASA SMD Software Workshop 2024
Washington D.C.

About Me

- GISer
- Engineer
- Earth AI practitioner
- Long time contributor to open source software projects
- Research interests include:
 - snow water equivalent monitoring and forecasting
 - ozone estimation enhancement
 - wildfire spreading forecasting

New tech is changing NASA research rapidly and it becomes very difficult for silo studies to succeed.

We need to break silos by improving workflow tangibility and reusability/reproducibility.

New research paradigm need new software

Geoweaver & AI Research Productivity

- Productivity tool to boost your research projects and team collaboration
- Preserve records and keep complicated workflows tangible and transferable among team members or across teams

Landing Site:

<https://geoweaver.dev>

Geoweaver: <https://github.com/ESIPFed/Geoweaver>

PyGeoweaver:

<https://github.com/ESIPFed/pygeoweaver>

GEOWEAVER

Build **Workflows** That Scale

An open-source, in-browser tool for simplifying data processing workflows with high-performance server support, featuring code history and workflow orchestration.

 Github

 Guide

 Demo

Comparison to Jupyter Routine

```
Code History
1 """
2 **Synthetic Earth Science Data Analyzer**
3
4 This Python program generates synthetic temperature data
5 for multiple locations and months and then performs basic
6 statistical analysis on the generated data. It includes
7 functions to calculate the average, maximum, and minimum
8 temperatures for specific locations and months. The
9 'monthly_statistics' function compiles and displays
10 temperature statistics for all locations in a given month.
11 This program is designed for educational purposes to
12 illustrate how to analyze Earth science-related data and
13 can serve as a starting point for more complex research
14 projects in the field of Earth science, environmental
15 science, or climate analysis.
16
17 """
18
19 import random
20
21 # Simulate data for different locations and months
22 locations = ["Location A", "Location B", "Location C"]
23 months = ["January", "February", "March", "April", "May",
24 "June"]
25 data = {}
26
27 # Generate synthetic temperature data for each location
28 and month
29 for location in locations:
30     data[location] = {month: random.uniform(0, 40) for
31 month in months}
32
33 def average_temperature(location, month):
34     """
35     Calculate the average temperature for a specific
36     location and month.
37
38     Args:
39     location (str): The location for which to
```

```
File Edit View Run Kernel Tabs Settings Help
sample_forecast.ipynb Python 3 (ipykernel)
Sample Weather Forecasting
Synthetic Earth Science Data Analyzer
This Python program generates synthetic temperature data for multiple locations and
months and then performs basic statistical analysis on the generated data. It includes
functions to calculate the average, maximum, and minimum temperatures for specific
locations and months. The monthly_statistics function compiles and displays
temperature statistics for all locations in a given month. This program is designed for
educational purposes to illustrate how to analyze Earth science-related data and can
serve as a starting point for more complex research projects in the field of Earth science,
environmental science, or climate analysis.
[3]: import random
# Simulate data for different locations and months
locations = ["Location A", "Location B", "Location C"]
months = ["January", "February", "March", "April", "May", "June"]
data = {}
# Generate synthetic temperature data for each location and month
for location in locations:
    data[location] = {month: random.uniform(0, 40) for month in months}
def average_temperature(location, month):
    """
    Calculate the average temperature for a specific location and month.
    Args:
```

Ability to Preserve History

```
Code History
1 """
2 **Synthetic Earth Science Data Analyzer**
3
4 This Python program generates synthetic temperature data
5 for multiple locations and months and then performs basic
6 statistical analysis on the generated data. It includes
7 functions to calculate the average, maximum, and minimum
8 temperatures for specific locations and months. The
9 'monthly_statistics' function compiles and displays
10 temperature statistics for all locations in a given month.
11 This program is designed for educational purposes to
12 illustrate how to analyze Earth science-related data and
13 can serve as a starting point for more complex research
14 projects in the field of Earth science, environmental
15 science, or climate analysis.
16
17 """
18
19 import random
20
21 # Simulate data for different locations and months
22 locations = ["Location A", "Location B", "Location C"]
23 months = ["January", "February", "March", "April", "May",
24           "June"]
25 data = {}
26
27 # Generate synthetic temperature data for each location
28 and month
29 for location in locations:
30     data[location] = {month: random.uniform(0, 40) for
31                       month in months}
32
33 def average_temperature(location, month):
34     """
35     Calculate the average temperature for a specific
36     location and month.
37
38     Args:
39         location (str): The location for which to
```

```
Logging
----- Start to execute Process fB0mSKIdNRvI
Process fB0mSKIdNRvI Started
Monthly Statistics for March:
Location A:
Average Temperature: 23.56°C
Max Temperature: 23.56°C
Min Temperature: 9.88°C
Location B:
Average Temperature: 20.75°C
Max Temperature: 23.56°C
Min Temperature: 9.88°C
Location C:
Average Temperature: 9.88°C
Max Temperature: 23.56°C
Min Temperature: 9.88°C
Exit Code: 0
The process fB0mSKIdNRvI is finished.
----- Process fB0mSKIdNRvI ended
```

The screenshot shows a JupyterLab environment. On the left, a file browser displays a directory structure with files like 'anaconda3', 'gw-works...', 'h2', 'jdk', 'Anaconda...', 'geoweaver...', 'geoweaver...', 'jdk.tar.gz', 'nohup.out', and 'sample_fore...'. A tooltip for 'sample_forecast.ipynb' shows its details: Name: sample_forecast.ipynb, Size: 5.6 KB, Created: 2023-10-31 10:05:06, Modified: 2023-10-31 10:05:06, Writable: true, Kernel: Python 3 (ipykernel).

The main area shows a code editor with the following content:

Sample Weather Forecasting

Synthetic Earth Science Data Analyzer

This Python program generates synthetic temperature data for multiple locations and months and then performs basic statistical analysis on the generated data. It includes functions to calculate the average, maximum, and minimum temperatures for specific locations and months. The `monthly_statistics` function compiles and displays temperature statistics for all locations in a given month. This program is designed for educational purposes to illustrate how to analyze Earth science-related data and can serve as a starting point for more complex research projects in the field of Earth science, environmental science, or climate analysis.

```
[4]: import random
# Simulate data for different locations and m
locations = ["Location A", "Location B", "Loc
months = ["January", "February", "March", "Ap
data = {}
```


User Ad-hoc
Requirements
v.s.
Software Design
& Features

Our Experiences so far

Before adoption of Geoweaver:

- Each team member (e.g., RA) needs at least half a year to fully onboard
- A lot of back and forth communication, wasted a lot of time on old stubborn issues

After adoption of Geoweaver:

- Each member (including masters) takes **one week** to import the workflow and **already start to contribute in the first month**
- We (**currently five people team**) are maintaining three workflows at the same time and all are working great
- Much less explanation communication in Email/Slack/meetings
- People come and go and nothing lost.
- People who left are missing Geoweaver, and people on the team are happy.

ESIP ML Cluster

Community chat: Monthly Meeting: Every 3rd Friday 12:00 PM EST

<https://www.esipfed.org/get-involved/community-calendar>

Welcome!

Thank You!
Questions?

Contact: zsun@gmu.edu

